

Thermal Decomposition of Potassium Persulphate in the Aqueous Media*

M. BANDYOPADHYAY and R. S. KONAR

Department of Chemistry, R. E. College, Durgapur-9

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The thermal decomposition of potassium persulphate in the aqueous media at a pH-8 (Phosphate-buffer), has been studied in the temperature range 60° to 95.5° in the concentration range 0.1 to 10.0 g/lit., with a view to establishing the reaction mechanism. The reaction has been followed by the conventional iodometric technique in a static system, and it has been confirmed that the reaction occurs in several elementary steps involving free radicals, and the process is a non-chain one. The overall kinetic order for the disappearance of persulphate is unity, in agreement with the findings of the previous workers and the overall activation energy is about 28.0 kcal/mole and H₂O₂ is not a product of the reaction.

It has been found that the following mechanism is consistent with the analytical data under the experimental conditions.

It has been deduced that

$$k_1 = 10^{12.903} \exp(-27600/1.987T) \text{sec}^{-1}$$

If the activation energy for the geminate recombination of SO₄^{·-} in the solvent cage be taken as zero then E is the measure of the bond dissociation energy (B.D.E.) of the -O-O- bond in the persulphate.

WHILE considerable amount of work has been done on the thermal decomposition of potassium persulphate in the aqueous media, the mechanism is still not clearly understood. The earlier work in this field has been reviewed by House¹ in 1962, but the bulk of the work is concerned with the decomposition of S₂O₈⁻⁻ ions catalysed by metal ions, organic and inorganic reducing agents. The most significant work in the uncatalysed thermal decomposition of persulphate in the aqueous media in neutral or buffer solutions at a pH about 8, are those of Bartlett and Cotman Jr.² and of Kolthoff and Miller³.

Bartlett *et. al* found the overall order of the reaction is unity and postulated two mechanisms to explain the 1st order kinetics.

(i) non-chain free radical process viz.,

and (ii) free radical chain process

Kolthoff *et. al* made a detailed analytical study in H₂O¹⁸ media as well, and found that in neutral solution, the evolved oxygen came from the solvent molecules but not from the persulphate ions, and also noted the overall activation energy for the decomposition of persulphate in neutral media as 33.5 kcal/mol. Kolthoff *et. al.* concluded that the first mechanism was acceptable but could not discount the chain process.

Bawn and Margerison⁴ studied the reaction in the presence of excess of DPPH (α - α -diphenyl- β -picrylhydrazyl) in 1:1 water-alcohol media. Assuming that sulphate ion radicals are removed by DPPH only and not at all by alcohol or water molecules, they found that rate constant (k_1) as

$$k_1 = 3.7 \times 10^{13} \exp\{(-28,300/1.987T)\} \text{sec}^{-1}$$

Since K₂S₂O₈ is a potential initiator in radical polymerization in emulsion⁵ and in aqueous media⁶, it is desirable that its decomposition mechanism must be established before getting any insight into the mechanism of emulsion polymerization. Further, it has recently been reported that the decomposition of S₂O₈⁻⁻ ions are catalysed by soaps and detergents⁷ in the aqueous media. In view of these uncertainties, we decided to reinvestigate briefly the thermal decomposition of persulphate in aqueous media of pH -8. Here we are reporting the results obtained in some 100 experiments.

Experimental

The quality of chemicals used were of B.D.H. and E. Merck (G.R.) grade. Potassium persulphate (E.

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Marck G.R.) was recrystallised from conductivity water several times. The reaction was carried out in an electrically controlled water thermostat ($t \pm 0.01^\circ$). The temperature was measured with a Hg- thermometer. Phosphate buffer solution was prepared by the method of Bartlett and Cotman Jr. The pH of each mixture sample was measured with a Cambridge pH-meter before and after the time of residence at 25° . The pH was found to remain unaltered. But when the pH was measured at elevated temperature, viz., 60° to 95° , the pH of the reaction mixture was found to increase slightly i.e., by one unit approximately. The decomposition of persulphate was followed by the conventional iodometric method. At high temperature, the reaction was quenched by cooling it to a lower temperature (30° to 35°) by adding ice cold water¹.

Results

The thermal decomposition of potassium persulphate in aqueous media was studied at pH 8 in the temperature range 60° to 95.5° and in the concentration range 0.10 to 10.0 g/lit. It has been found that the rate constant measured at a given temperature using E. Marck (G.R.) persulphate is higher than that obtained with the same persulphate recrystallised from conductivity water. This fact is substantiated by the following data².

TABLE 1

Persulphate	(K ₂ S ₂ O ₈) M	pH	Temp. °C	k _{obs} ⁻¹	Reference
E. Marck (G.R.)	0.03	8.0	60	4.2×10^{-4}	this work
	0.02	8.0	„	2.93×10^{-4}	8
	0.07	neutral	„	4.13×10^{-4}	9
E. Marck (G.R.) recrystallised	0.03	8.0	„	3.4×10^{-4}	this work

The uncertainty involved in measuring the rate constants is about 5%.

In view of the impurity effects, the experiments were conducted with the recrystallised persulphate. It has been observed that the overall decomposition

TABLE 2

Temp. in °K	k × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹	Overall reaction order
333.0	3.40	0.98 ± 0.05
342.0	9.83	1.04 ± 0.02
346.0	14.80	1.02 ± 0.05
368.5	170.00	1.08 ± 0.02

of persulphate obeys first order kinetics at all temperatures and at all concentrations. At a given temperature and a given concentration the rate

of initial decomposition was determined by plotting x/t Vs. t , and extrapolating it to zero time, where x is the amount of persulphate (expressed in moles) decomposed in time t . The order of the reaction was determined by plotting log (initial rate) Vs. log (concn.). The results are summarised in Table 2.

Discussion

It has been shown experimentally in the emulsion polymerization⁵ and also in the aqueous polymerization initiated by persulphate that SO₄^{·-} and OH radicals are the reactive intermediates in the thermal decomposition of persulphates in the aqueous media. The most probable step in the persulphate dissociation is therefore, the reaction (1) i.e.,

It has been shown¹ that the geminate recombination of the SO₄^{·-} radical ions in the solvent cage does not occur to a significant extent, and hence the back reaction (i.e., reaction 1) need not be considered in the mechanism⁽¹⁾. Further, any thermal reaction involving two non-geminate SO₄^{·-} ion radicals which may react outside the solvent cage is not likely to be significant, because chemical reactions leading to bond formation between two similarly charged species are less probable on electrostatic grounds. Hence to all intents and purposes, the back reaction of (1) is not important; in other words, the equilibrium, viz., $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{--} \rightarrow 2\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ will not exist in the aqueous media. The SO₄^{·-} ion radicals then formed will disappear by the reaction (2), producing OH radicals

The OH radicals may attack the S₂O₈⁻⁻ ions

and may also annihilate each other, i.e.,

A steady state treatment of the chain reactions (1), (2), (3) and (4) gives

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{--}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{--}] + k_4 \left(\frac{k_1}{k_2}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{--}]^{3/2}$$

Since the reaction is 1st order, the above mechanism does not satisfy the kinetic data. Reaction (4) may occur in solution but it is difficult to envisage such a reaction, particularly when Kolthoff *et. al.* have shown that the oxygen evolved at pH 8 or neutral media comes from the H₂O molecule only and not from the persulphate ions. Thus if,

occurs, it must proceed as follows :

where (*) denotes oxygen from water molecules. This reaction is certainly difficult to envisage and even if it does occur, it appears that it will face high energy barrier compared to the reaction (3). The reaction (5) was primarily postulated by Bartlett *et. al.* to give the correct kinetic reaction order in the chain decomposition of persulphate. It seems therefore that the major termination step is the reaction (3) and not (5) and a steady state treatment of the reactions (1), (2) and (3) gives

$$-d \frac{[S_2O_8^{--}]}{dt} = k_1 [S_2O_8^{--}]$$

while experimentally,

$$-d \frac{[S_2O_8^{--}]}{dt} = k_{exp} \times [S_2O_8^{--}]$$

hence $k_1 = k_{exp}$

From the Arrhenius treatment of the data (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Shows the Arrhenius plot of $\log_{10} k_1$

$$k_1 = 10^{12.90 \pm 0.08} \exp\{(-27,600 \pm 250)/1,987T\} \text{ sec}^{-1}.$$

If the activation energy of the geminate recombination of two $SO_4^{\cdot -}$ ion radicals be taken as zero, then E_1 is obviously a measure of the B.D.E. of the -O-O- bond in the persulphate molecule. We conclude that the most probable mechanism of the thermal decomposition of persulphate in the aqueous media at pH 8 is given by the reactions (1), (2) and (3).

We have searched for H_2O_2 after the reaction by the pertitanic acid test with the help of a UV-spectro-

photometer (Unicam-SP-500). The detectability limit is about 10^{-5} (moles/l) at 400 mn. Hence, H_2O_2 if formed, must be less than this value. It is surprising that H_2O_2 is not a product of the reaction under the experimental conditions, although it is well known that in the gas phase, reaction (3) gives H_2O_2 . It is suggested that in the aqueous media OH radicals remain associated with the water molecules, and the water molecules are involved in the transition state of the reaction (3). It is suggested that a ring complex of the type shown in the figure 2

Fig. 2. Shows the mode of combination of OH radicals in the aqueous media.

is formed in the transition state of the reaction (3) due to extensive hydrogen bonding. The number of water molecules associated with a hydroxyl radical at a given temperature is not known. The simplest model seems to be a OH radical with one H_2O molecule.

The Arrhenius parameters obtained in this work agree very well with those of Bawn *et. al.* who got the numbers via an indirect method.

It seems that, the activation energy found for the reaction (1) by Kolthoff *et. al.* is slightly on the higher side.

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